

ENUMERATION OF VARIANTS OF *BACILLUS* FROM DAIRY ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLESSireesha Kalangi¹; Ramachandra B.²; Venkatesh M.³; Shankarappa Bajantri⁴, Prabha R^{5*}1 M.Tech (Dairy Microbiology), Department of Dairy Microbiology, Dairy Science College, KVAFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru (Karnataka), India; kalangisireesha@gmail.com 97048549702 Associate Professor & Head, Department of Dairy Microbiology, Dairy Science College, KVAFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru (Karnataka), India; ramudscb@gmail.com; 99641366153 Professor, Department of Dairy technology, Dairy Science College, KVAFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India; venkatm1965@rediffmail.com; 94493562634 Associate Professor, Department of Livestock Farm Complex, Veterinary College, KVFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru (Karnataka), India; drshankarbhantri@gmail.com; 83100062735 – Associate Professor (Retd.), Department of Dairy Microbiology, Dairy Science College, KVFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru (Karnataka), India; raoprabharao@gmail.com;Corresponding author: **Prabha R*** raoprabharao@gmail.com

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Abstract

The present study is aimed to enumerate *Bacillus*, acid tolerant as well bile tolerant *Bacillus* which may help to find the probiotic strains of *Bacillus* distributed in dairy environmental samples. All the dairy environmental samples showed total bacterial and *Bacillus* counts in the range of 0.6 to 8.42 and 0 to 5.42 log₁₀cfu/g or ml, respectively. Acid tolerant *Bacillus* counts were found in dung, can rinse, udder swab of milch animal, milker's hand swab and can rinse at 3.40, 2.22, 1.9, 1.55 log₁₀cfu/g or ml, respectively. The silage and milking parlour air samples revealed 2.96 log₁₀cfu/g and 0.07 log₁₀cfu/min of acid tolerant *Bacillus* counts, while bile tolerant *Bacillus* were at 2.91 log₁₀cfu/g and 0.1 log₁₀cfu/min indicating that silage and air had both variants of *Bacillus* counts. The samples which did not show the presence of acid and bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts were soil, feed, water and all the milk samples (aseptic milk, pail milk, can milk chilled milk and pasteurized milk).

Key words: Dairy environmental samples, Probiotic, Acid tolerant *Bacillus*, Bile tolerant *Bacillus*, Variants

Introduction

In recent years, a number of *Bacillus* spp. have been reported as novel probiotics. *Bacillus* species share the sporulation ability, forming one oval endospore per cell. This is a crucial feature for *Bacillus* spp. to survive environmental stress and harsh conditions of growth, preservation, storage and distribution (Jezewska-Frackowiak *et al.*, 2018). Recently, some thermo-tolerant *Bacillus* members, including *Bacillus coagulans*, *Bacillus licheniformis*, and other *Bacillus* strains, were considered as new lactic acid producers. Compared to the lactic acid fermentation under mesophilic conditions, lactic acid producers of thermophilic *Bacillus* species have been shown to be promising in industrial-scale fermentations with a low energy and a low risk for contamination. *Bacillus* spp. produce L-lactic acid, it does not produce gas from maltose, raffinose, mannitol and sucrose fermentation (Li *et al.*, 2019).

Bacillus species are Gram-positive, spore-forming, rod-shaped, aerobic or facultative anaerobic bacteria, and they are ubiquitously distributed in soil, water, the environment as well as various food products. By virtue of their multilayer-structured endospores, *Bacillus* spp. offer high tolerance towards acid, dehydration, γ -ray and ultraviolet radiation; they are stable during heat processing and low-temperature storage. Generally *Bacillus* pp. are related to spoilage and food poisoning (*Bacillus cereus*). Few strains of *Bacillus cereus* in now used as probiotic strain. Commercial *B. cereus* strains for human use are available; these include Biosubtyl^{DL} (*B. cereus*), Bactisubtil (*B. cereus* IP 5832), and Subtyl (*B. cereus* var. *vietnami*). Some studies have investigated their safety including identification, toxin production, and transferable antibiotic resistance (Zhu *et al.*, 2016). Several *Bacillus* strains have been screened for their potential probiotic functionalities in animal husbandry, bionematicides, production of biosurfactants and antibiotic alternatives through production of bacteriocins. Additionally, they have also been verified to possess pathogen exclusion, anti-oxidant, immuno-modulatory and food fermentation abilities. Recent studies have investigated various *Bacillus* strains, including *B. clausii*, *B. pumilus*, *B. polyfermenticus*, and *B. subtilis*. The use of *Bacillus* stains as potential probiotics need to be investigated thoroughly only once their nature to transfer genes related to antimicrobial resistance, production of enterotoxins and biogenic amines in the human gut are negated. *Bacillus* probiotics have been shown to temporarily reside as symbiotic organisms within the host (Lee *et al.*, 2019).

Many literatures mainly include isolation of *Bacillus* species from samples but enumeration or count of *Bacillus* is very few. There is a dearth of information in the literature regarding variants of *Bacillus* counts such as acid tolerant, bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts in dairy environmental samples. Hence, the present study had been taken up to get the data on total bacteria, total *Bacillus* count, acid tolerant *Bacillus* and bile tolerance *Bacillus* counts directly from dairy environmental samples which may help in future to isolate *Bacillus* species with probiotic nature. Since the literatures are not readily available for such counts whatever available are presented here. According to Ledina *et al.* (2021), the expansive physiology of *Bacillus* spp., has allowed its members to colonize almost all natural habitats, such as soil, air, lake sediments and even extreme environments. As *Bacillus* spp. can be isolated from soil (which was until recently considered as their main habitat) and environments contaminated with soil, their presence on dairy farms is inevitable. These microorganisms contaminate raw milk primarily at the farm level (e.g., during milking, raw milk storage and handling on the farm) with potential for recontamination to occur at various points along the dairy production continuum from farm to final product (during transport or at the processing plant). Cow's teats are considered as a major source of spores in raw milk mainly due to contamination from bedding, feed and dust. The members of the genus *Bacillus* are ubiquitous and have been isolated from dairy farm environments, including silage, pasture, soil, bedding material, faces, water and feed.

Madika *et al.* (2017) isolated 11 *Bacillus* from 15 soil samples collected from botanical garden, refuse dump sites and flower beds after subjecting 1 dilution to 80 °C/10 min, further dilutions carried out further ad pour plated using nutrient agar with incubation at 37 °C/24 - 48 h. Ostrov *et al.* (2019) obtained dairy-associated bacterial isolates of 5 numbers from Israeli dairy farms from goat (3) and cow milk (2) samples and identified as *Bacillus* species based on their morphology and their ability to form spores. From five New York dairy farms, a total of 355 rinse of towel used to wipe udder and bulk tank raw milk samples were collected that revealed *Bacillus* counts of 0.15 to 2.8 log₁₀cfu/ml and 1.0 to 1.7 log₁₀ cfu/ml (Evanowski *et al.*, 2020).

Different feed, milk, egg and human stool of totally 180 samples, 67 and 37% of samples revealed above 10,000 CFU/g of total viable count and total *Bacillus* count, respectively as per Haque *et al.* (2022).

A study by Peng *et al.* (2023), the aerobic plate count (APC) and aerobic *Bacillus* abundance were determined in 435 raw milk, 451 pasteurized milk, and 617 sterilized milk samples collected from 13 Chinese provinces (or municipalities). Raw milk showed APC of 4.55 while aerobic *Bacillus* count of 2.00 log₁₀cfu/ml whereas APC in pasteurized milk was 2.83 followed by 1.67 of aerobic *Bacillus* count of 2.00 log₁₀cfu/ml. In case of sterilized milk the counts were 1.45; 1.08 for APC and aerobic *Bacillus*, respectively. The proportions of aerobic *Bacillus* in raw milk, pasteurized milk and sterilized milk were 54.02%, 14.41%, and 1.30%, respectively.

An attempt has been done in the present study to obtain the counts of *Bacillus*, acid tolerant *Bacillus* and bile tolerance *Bacillus* from dairy environmental samples. This may aid in obtaining *Bacillus* isolates with probiotic characteristic directly.

Materials and Methods

Dairy environmental samples were collected and subjected to enumeration of total bacterial count, total *Bacillus* count and variants of *Bacillus* counts.

Collection of Samples

Dairy environmental samples like soil, dung, feed, fodder, silage, swab of milch animal udder, milker's hand swab, rinse of milking pail, can, air, water, pail milk, can milk samples from Department of Instructional Livestock and Farm Complex, College of Veterinary Science, KVAFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru and milk samples like chilled milk, pasteurized milk collected from Student Experimental Dairy Plant, Dairy Science College, KVAFSU, Hebbal, Bengaluru for the purpose to enumerate and isolate *Bacillus* species were collected in sterile labelled sample bottles. The samples were analysed for total bacterial count and *Bacillus* counts as per Harrigan (1998).

Enumeration of *Bacillus* species from dairy environmental samples

Solid samples of 11 g were transferred to 99 ml of sterile phosphate buffer to make 1:10 dilution and heated to in water bath maintained at 80°C /10 min. The liquid sample directly heated to 80°C /10 min. in water bath and 1 dilution was carried out. Further required dilutions were prepared serially using 1st dilution. Serially diluted samples were transferred to labelled sterile petri plates in triplicates: one set for Total Bacterial Count (TBC); second set for total *Bacillus* count, third set for acid tolerant *Bacillus* count and fourth set for . Molten sterile media was poured to labelled plates such as for TBC – SPCA; for total *Bacillus* count - Sterile molten 2 % Nutrient Agar (NA), acid tolerant *Bacillus* spp. – acidified 2% NA (Sterile HCL of 1N added to molten nutrient agar medium for adjusting the pH to 2.0 before pouring to the plates) and bile tolerant *Bacillus* count – ox bile (0.3 %) incorporated 2 % NA, plates were allowed to solidify. All the poured plates were incubated at 37 °C /24-48 h by inverting the plates. After the completion of the incubation period, the colonies on nutrient agar were counted. The countable plates ranging between 30-300 were counted and average count was expressed as log₁₀cfu/g or ml or min.

Result and Discussion

All the dairy environmental samples collected were plated using standard plate count agar for total bacterial count, Nutrient agar (NA) with 2% agar for total *Bacillus* count acidified nutrient agar (pH 2.0) for acid tolerant *Bacillus* and 0.3% bile incorporated NA for bile tolerant *Bacillus* and incubated at 37 °C for 24 to 48 h.

Bacillus spp in solid dairy environmental samples

Among the solid dairy environmental samples like soil, feed, fodder, dung and silage of dairy farm of the university, dung had high bacterial count, total *Bacillus* and acid tolerant *Bacillus* counts of 8.42, 5.42 and 3.4 log₁₀cfu/g, respectively. The soil sample showed lower count of bacteria, total *Bacillus* of 4.68, 4.35 log₁₀ cfu/g while acid tolerant *Bacillus* were absent in soil, feed and fodder. Fodder had high bile tolerant *Bacillus* count of 4.71 log₁₀ cfu/g while absent in soil, feed and dung. Significant difference was noticed among the *Bacillus* counts among solid dairy environmental samples with respect to total *Bacillus*, acid and bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts. Total

bacterial count helped to know the per cent occurrence of aerobic spore count among samples plated. Soil, feed, fodder, dung and silage possessed 92.94, 94.41, 83.65, 64.37 and 64.16 per cent of total *Bacillus* count, respectively out of total bacterial count. Dung and silage possessed 62.73 and 54.91 per cent of acid tolerant *Bacillus* count, whereas fodder and silage samples showed 98.94 and 53.98 per cent of bile tolerant *Bacillus* count out of total *Bacillus* count (Table 1). Silage sample had both acid as well bile tolerant *Bacillus*.

Bacillus spp in liquid dairy environmental samples

The liquid based dairy farm samples like udder swab, hand swab, pail rinse, can rinse, water, aseptic milk, pail milk, can milk, pasteurized milk and air were plated for total bacteria, total *Bacillus*, acid and bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts. Out of these samples, can milk and chilled milk samples showed high bacterial counts of 7.6 log₁₀ cfu/ml while pail rinse had lowest count of 2.36 log₁₀ cfu/ml. Aseptic milk had high total *Bacillus* count of 2.4 log₁₀ cfu/ml while other samples showed lower counts. Can rinse sample had high acid tolerant *Bacillus* count of 2.22 log₁₀ cfu/ml while remaining samples showed lower counts. Air sample of milk parlour showed 0.1 log₁₀ cfu/m of bile tolerant *Bacillus* count while other counts were nil. Significant difference was noticed among the variants of *Bacillus* counts among liquid dairy environmental samples with respect to total *Bacillus*, acid and bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts. Total bacterial count helped to know the per cent occurrence of total *Bacillus* count among samples plated. Udder swab, hand swab, can rinse, water, aseptic milk, can milk, and air possessed 81.64, 62.11, 68.78, 57.78, 40.33, 30.26 and 33.33 per cent of total *Bacillus* count out of total bacterial count. Udder swab, hand swab, can rinse and air samples possessed 87.15, 77.50, 93.27 and 35.0 per cent of acid tolerant *Bacillus* count. Air sample showed 50 per cent bile tolerant *Bacillus* count out of aerobic spore count (Table 2). Only milking parlour air had both acid as well bile tolerant *Bacillus*.

On the contrary, when Al-Allaf (2011) enumerated *Bacillus* spp from twelve samples such as air, water, milk and cheese from areas of Iraq. The higher counts were noticed in air (70 %) followed by milk of (60 %) and water (50 %) and cheese (30 %) compared with the present study where in water had higher count (58 %) followed by milk (35 %) and air (33 %) samples of dairy environment. Madika *et al.* (2017) observed 80 per cent *Bacillus* spp. from soil samples of refuse dump site and 20 per cent of botanical garden of department of biological sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.

Ostrov *et al.* (2019) obtained dairy-associated bacterial isolates of 5 numbers from Israeli dairy farms from goat (3) and cow milk (2) samples and identified as *Bacillus* species based on their morphology and their ability to form spores. From five New York dairy farms, a total of 355 rinse of towel used to wipe udder and bulk tank raw milk samples were collected that revealed *Bacillus* counts of 0.15 to 2.8 log₁₀cfu/ml and 1.0 to 1.7 log₁₀ cfu/ml (Evanowski *et al.*, 2020). Haque *et al.* (2022) disclosed that 67 and 39% samples of feed, milk, egg and human stool samples (180 nos.) had above 10,000 CFU/g of total viable count and total *Bacillus* count, respectively. The proportions of aerobic *Bacillus* in raw milk, pasteurized milk and sterilized milk were 54.02%, 14.41%, and 1.30%, respectively was noticed by Peng *et al.* (2023), in 435 raw milk, 451 pasteurized milk, and 617 sterilized milk samples collected from 13 Chinese provinces. It is evident from the present study that variants of *Bacillus* obtained especially acid as well bile tolerant ones may be isolated and considered as probiotic isolates with further screening for probiotic characteristics.

Conclusion

Acid tolerant *Bacillus* counts were found in dung, can rinse, udder swab of milch animal, milker's hand swab and can rinse. The silage and milking parlour air samples revealed both acid tolerant as well bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts. Soil, feed, water, aseptic milk, pail milk, can milk, chilled milk and pasteurized milk did not reveal the presence of acid and bile tolerant *Bacillus* counts. Further research to

isolate probiotic *Bacillus* strains having acid and bile tolerance may be possible from the data of the present study.

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Table 1: Enumeration of Total bacteria and variants of *Bacillus* spp from solid dairy environmental samples

SL. No	Source	Bacteriological parameters carried out			
		Total Bacterial Count	Variants of <i>Bacillus</i> counts		
			Total <i>Bacillus</i>	Acid tolerant <i>Bacillus</i>	Bile tolerant <i>Bacillus</i>
log ₁₀ cfu/g					
1	Soil	4.68 ^{bc}	4.35 ^{bc}	0.00	0.00
2	Feed	5.01 ^{bc}	4.73 ^{abc}	0.00	0.00
3	Fodder	5.69 ^{bc}	4.76 ^{abc}	0.00	4.71 ^a
4	Dung	8.42 ^a	5.42 ^{ab}	3.40 ^a	0.00
5	Silage	8.40 ^a	5.39 ^{ab}	2.96 ^b	2.91 ^b
CD (P=.05)		0.34	0.34	0.23	0.23

Note:

Total *Bacillus* from samples selected by heating 1st dilution 80 °C/10 min and incubated at 37 °C/24-72 h. Medium used: Total Bacterial Count (TBC) – Standard Plate Count Agar (SPCA), Total *Bacillus* – 2 % Nutrient agar (NA), Acid tolerant *Bacillus* – 1N HCL 2 % NA, Bile tolerant *Bacillus* – 0.3 % ox bile in 2 % NA

Values are average of three trails

CD-Critical difference

Higher value in the table was compared with other values

Same superscripts with in the column indicate no significant difference

Different superscripts with in the column are compared with other values

Table 2: Enumeration of Total bacteria and variants of *Bacillus* spp from liquid dairy environmental samples

SL. No	Source	Microbiological parameters carried out				
		Total Bacterial Count	Variants of <i>Bacillus</i> counts			
			Total <i>Bacillus</i>	Acid tolerant <i>Bacillus</i>	Bile tolerant <i>Bacillus</i>	
log ₁₀ cfu/ml						
1	Udder swab	2.67 ^{efg}	2.18 ^{ab}	1.9 ^{abcd}	0	
2	Hand swab	3.22 ^{efg}	2.00 ^{abcd}	1.55 ^{cd}	0	
3	Pail rinse	2.36 ^{fg}	0	0	0	
4	Can rinse	3.46 ^{ef}	2.38 ^{ab}	2.22 ^{ab}	0	
5	Water (37°C)	2.44 ^{efg}	2.39	1.41 ^{cd}	0	0
6	Aseptic milk	5.95 ^{cd}	2.4 ^{ab}	0	0	
7	Pail milk	7.5 ^{ab}	0	0	0	
8	Can milk	7.6 ^a	2.3 ^{ab}	0	0	
9	Chilled milk	7.6 ^a	0	0	0	
10	Pasteurized milk	6.2 ^{cd}	0	0	0	
11	Air	0.6 ^h	0.2 ^e	0.07 ^e	0.1 ^a	
CD (P=.05)		0.34	0.25	0.17	0	

Note:

Values are average of three trails

CD-Critical difference

Higher value in the table was compared with other values

Same superscripts with in the column indicate no significant difference at P=.05

Different superscripts with in the column are compared with other values.